

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	[101152452]
Project acronym:	[U-SPY]
Project name:	[Artificial metalloenzymes Using SPY protein]

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Date:	[30/09/2025]
Version:	[v2.0]

1. Data Summary

The re-use of existing data is not planned. The project involves characterization data (e.g. ^1H NMR spectra) of the applied substrates and metal complexes that will be compared to the publicly available experimental procedures and protocols (scientific publications and in their supplementary information) to check the purity of the synthesized compounds. New data will be generated throughout the timeline of the project, mostly in digital format, which will have an estimated size of 15 GB overall. The non-digital printed data will be also scanned and stored in accessible digital format. Possible experimental setup of prototypes of instrumentation will be described and the description supported by photographs.

Table 1. Collection of all the information about generated by the project.

File description	Origin	Purpose	Format	Software	Research objectives	Size
Previously published scientific papers	Repository of scientific journals	Comparison of characterization data with the locally recorded ones.	pdf docx	Adobe Acrobat Reader Microsoft Office Word	RO1, RO2, RO3, RO4	~50 MB all
Laboratory notebook	Handwritten by the researcher	To record the amounts of chemicals used for reactions and the used protocols for reactions and measurements.	Laboratory notes in paper	-	RO1, RO2, RO3, RO4	Two paper notes
Mass spectra	PC connected to HPLC-MS	Validation of the structure and purity of newly synthesized compounds and reaction products.	folder containing dat, idx, max, sig, sts, txt and inf files; after processing the data: pdf	MassLynx	RO1, RO2, RO3, RO4	~60 MB /spectrum
NMR spectra	PC connected to NMR spectrometer.		a folder containing various parameter, txt and acquisition files; after processing the data: mnova file	MestreNova	RO1, RO4	~1 MB /spectrum
UV-visible spectra	PC connected to spectrophotometer	Characterization of newly synthesized compounds. Determination of concentrations and stability constants.	csv, xlsx and obj files	Microsoft Office Excel and Origin	RO1, RO2, RO3, RO4	~1-10 MB /spectrum series
Fluorescence spectra	PC connected to fluorimeter					
Models of artificial metalloenzymes	Rosetta and AlphaFold softwares/web servers	To build <i>in silico</i> models for the constructed metalloenzymes and to plan further improvements.	pdb files	Pymol	RO3	~100 MB /model
Calculation of stability constants	Hyperquad2014, HypSpec	Concentrations, stability constants and molar spectra of compounds.	hqd files	HypSpec	RO2, RO3	~1MB /file
Processed data	All the previous datafiles collected, the lab notes digitalized by scanning	Make all data easily available.	pdf files	Adobe Acrobat Reader	RO1, RO2, RO3, RO4	~5 GB

Data utility:

Outside the project, the generated data might be of two types and be accessed and used by different researchers:

1. Re-collection of previously reported data: the procedures for the synthesis, and for the structural and functional characterization of the compounds, and in general of all previously reported protocols may be carried out. The purpose will be that of obtaining a confirmation and/or refinement of the previously published data and background. The use of previously reported protocols, along with modifications of them, will be properly referenced in new generated data. This data will be useful for peptide chemists who intend to connect organic ligands or metal complexes to peptide with the same method. The collection of the functionalization methods – together with the modified ones – might be valuable in case of a coupling reaction does not work or the ligand/metal complex is not compatible with given reactants, as it will provide alternative solutions.
2. New generated data:
 - A. Members of the group of Prof. Tegoni, who will use these generated data in the framework of their project on Spy protein.
 - B. The optimized catalytic conditions will be also important for future catalytic applications and the *in silico* models of SpyCatcher and SpyTags may be used for docking studies by experts of the field of biocatalysis, who intend to construct SPY-based enzymes, especially in case of industrial applications.

2. FAIR data**2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata**

All deposited data will have a persistent digital object identifier provided by Zenodo. The researcher will also provide a permanent link on his ORCID page in order to make the data easier to trace. In the laboratory, the laboratory notebooks are stored in a dedicated place and distinguished by writing the name of the researcher on their coverings, where they will be stored also after the project's end. Descriptive, structural and legal metadata will be created for each uploaded file to ease the possibility for discovery, containing such information as resource type, title, version, publication date, author(s), keywords and subjects, language, grant and related works. Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in the repository immediately after publishing.

2.2. Making data accessible

The researcher keeps the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” concept.

- Before publication of manuscripts or patenting: data will be available for group members already before publication of the results, through a cloud storage (Google Drive).

- After publication of manuscript: all the connected data and preprints will be deposited in Zenodo and in IRIS which are trusted repositories (the latter one is the repository of UNIPR), and everyone will be able to download the pdf files from Zenodo and with university account from IRIS. Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of Zenodo, in the next 10 years.

Repository:

Depositing the data require no special arrangements; data will be uploaded via a standard procedure in Zenodo and in IRIS as soon as the preprints will be ready for submission to a peer-reviewed journal. By default, Zenodo registers a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each record (if it does not have already one), which is a globally unique and persistent identifier.

IRIS uses persistent identifiers by author (ORCID, Scopus ID) and by publication (DOI, Scopus ID, WoS ID, Pubmed ID).

Data:

- Before publication or patenting: according to the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” concept, raw and processed data will be restricted until patenting or publishing them in a scientific paper, to ensure novelty (mandatory prerequisite of patents) and to prevent the publication of the same data by others before the researcher (author and publisher rights).

- After publication or patenting: data will be openly available immediately via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) license. Data from Zenodo will be available without any further steps, while preprints can be downloaded from IRIS only after the logging in procedure (username and password), verifying the identity of the person accessing them. No embargo will be applied as all the research articles will be published in Open Access.

Metadata:

Metadata generated during the project will principally relate with instrument setup or data processing files. They will be openly available by applying the CC0 public domain dedication tool, which will be constantly updated. They will be available and findable at least in the next 10 years. Metadata is not guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available. At the end of the retention period, data will either be securely archived or disposed of in compliance with our data disposal procedures. Dataset will also include a README.txt file including the information about the software (with number of version) used for acquiring and processing the data.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- Processed data will be uploaded using PDF format, which allows the same appearance across all devices, while being compatible with all operating systems. Files will not be encrypted. For metadata standard English alphabetic characters, numbers and standard terms will be used (e.g. for keywords, filename, topic, etc.).

- Abbreviations will be explained in the README.txt file, and only the common ones will be used wherever it is applicable (e.g. for the amino acid sequence the widely used one-letter codes).

- A system in the measurement files will be used: to avoid general filenames (e.g. Titration1). The filename will include the measurements type (e.g. titration), the components (e.g. Cu(L1)_HEPES), the date (e.g. 2025-12-01) and that which repetition (with a number) was done. Moreover, for data treatment A-B-C-... letters will be used for the different methods, e.g. using different wavelength range for calculation. A typical title of a measurement file will look like titration-Cu(L1)_HEPES-2025-12-01-1A.

- It is not planned that data of U-SPY will re-use experimental data previously published. If it is inevitable, the uploaded data will contain references to previously published data(set) as qualified references, referring to the data(set) by its own persistent identifier and will describe the connection.

2.4. Increase data re-use

As mentioned earlier, datasets will include a README.txt file, which will also contain information about the methodologies used in the collection and procession of data (including the software versions used). This will facilitate data re-use, and others can test the reproducibility of the applied methodologies. Data will be freely available after publishing in Zenodo. By applying the CC-BY license, re-use of the data will be permitted during the project and also after the end of it. Data history will be present in Zenodo, as all versions will be available, showing clearly the changes in the given dataset.

3. Other research outputs

Management of research outputs other than data are here described, taking into account aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects in the following points.

In addition to the research data in digital and in paper form (notebooks), other research output will be also generated by the U-SPY project.

- Calculated protein models will be deposited in ModelArchive in pdb format, available for everyone. ModelArchive registers a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each record.
- The synthesized chemicals (linkers, peptides, proteins, substrates and products of reactions) will be stored in the fridges of the laboratory, in a dedicated holder, in micro centrifuge tubes and in centrifuge tubes, based on the amount. Their code, date of synthesis, amount and the name of the researcher (who synthesized) will be indicated on them with a label. The same information will be indicated also in the notes of the researcher and in an online storage of laboratory chemicals. This is in line with the FAIR principles: based on the codes and indicated location (metadata), chemicals will be findable and accessible for the members of the group during the lifetime of the project and after by the permission of the researcher and the group leader. Interoperability and re-use will be reached through indicating the synthesis methods and the characterization of the chemicals (such as NMR and MS spectra), which will also serve as reference for a future synthesis.

Updated version(s) of the DMP (after the first year of the project) will ensure the integrity of the data management of U-SPY and the DMP's timeliness.

4. Allocation of resources

The use of Zenodo repository for storing and archiving (for the next 10 years at least) research data and preprints is free of charge as well as data storage in cloud services (until limited storage).

Costs of open access publishing of peer-reviewed publications in full open access journals, which includes immediate deposit of a preprint in the depository of the scientific journal, will be covered by project funding (see below). Another cost covered by project funding will be the data storage on a portable SSD, necessary for data security and preservation (vide infra).

These costs will be covered by the "Institutional contributions: Research, training and networking contribution" budget of MSCA PF. The researcher (Dr. János Péter Mészáros) and his supervisor (Prof. Matteo Tegoni) will be responsible for the data management, The researcher and the supervisor will decide which data will be archived for long term in Zenodo.

5. Data security

To prevent an early, unauthorized access, data breach or a possible loss of data from cloud servers, an off-site backup will be used, which will be updated every week and stored in the laboratory, accessed by the researcher and his supervisor only. For this purpose, a portable SDD will be used, dedicated for the project. Data restoration procedures have been established to quickly recover data if needed.

From the date of publishing data will be safely stored in the trusted repositories for at least 10 years.

6. Ethics

Ethical data management consists of data quality assurance processes, timeliness, accuracy and transparency:

Data quality assurance processes: regularly the researcher will check and improve the data quality by applying data cleansing (e.g. identification of outliers, wrong measurement data excluded from the calculations indicated clearly), ensuring data fairness (avoiding biases) and integrity of the U-SPY project. Updated versions will be uploaded accordingly, and all versions will be visible.

Timeliness and accuracy: Through the update process, the researcher ensures that the most current and most accurate data will be available.

Transparency will be reached through the exact descriptions of methodology and software, giving the chance to repeat the measurement and test/validate in another laboratory.

Ethical issue arising described in the Description of Action: The synthesized chemicals (see **section 3**) may be potential causes of harm to the environment, animals and plants, and also they may potentially be hazardous in the laboratory. For these reasons, handling and storage will be carried out with the highest accuracy and according to the European, national and internal legislations (see Description of Action for more details). The described precaution and safety measures will be applied during the handling and storage.

7. Other issues

No other issues are identified and no other procedures will be applied for data management.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	31.03.2025	Initial version
2.0	30.09.2025	Minor corrections: typos, completing Table 1